

Supplementary Material: Systematic Mapping Protocol

Paper: Computational solutions for supporting systematic reviews in software engineering: a comprehensive overview

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1 Research Method

This study employs an SM as the research method. SM aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the research landscape on a specific topic, focusing on cataloging and classifying existing studies to identify trends, gaps, and areas requiring further investigation. The mapping process is structured into three main phases [1]: (i) **Planning**: aims to establish a review protocol defining the research questions, inclusion and exclusion criteria, study sources, search string, search strategy, and selection process; (ii) **Conducting**: searching and selecting the studies to extract and synthesize data from them; and (iii) **Reporting**: the results are used to answer the research questions. Afterward, the results are distributed to the targeted potentials. The main phases of the protocol used are presented in the following.

Research Questions Table 1 presents the Research Questions (RQ) that this SM aims to answer, as well as the justification for considering them.

Search String An initial set of terms was selected to construct the *search string*, and this set was iteratively refined until all pre-selected control group studies were found. The related works also helped refine the search string considered in this search:

(Tool OR System) AND (support OR Automat OR assist) AND (“Software Engineering” OR “computer science”) AND (SLR OR “systematic review” OR “literature review” OR “systematic mapping” OR “mapping study” OR “systematic map”)

Table 1: Research Questions and Rationale

N ^o	Research Question	Rationale
RQ1	<i>What type of studies have been published and when?</i>	This RQ provides understanding the specific publications on this topic and when they were published.
RQ2	<i>What computational approaches are available to support SR in SE?</i>	This research question aims to offer an overview of the proposed computational approach, e.g., type of approach (tool, script, algorithm), access, input, and output data.
RQ3	<i>How the computational approaches support SR?</i>	The objective of this RQ is to know how the coverage/semi-automation approach works considering the main phases/activities (e.g., study selection, evaluation, classification) of an SR.
RQ4	<i>What challenges have been reported regarding computational approaches to support SR?</i>	The goal of this question is to point out the specific open issues and future directions that may motivate further research in the area.

Source Scopus database was selected to perform this study, as it is the most widely used database in Computer Science [3, 5], with over 60 million records. Scopus indexes articles from other international publishers, including *Cambridge University Press*, *Association for Computing Machinery (ACM)*, *Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)*, *Nature Publishing Group*, *Springer*, *Wiley-Blackwell* and *Elsevier*.

To avoid missing relevant studies, we also applied the *Forward Snowballing* technique using Google Scholar, which is considered the most suitable database for this purpose [4].

Selection Criteria The selection criteria were organized into one inclusion criterion (IC) and seven exclusion criteria (EC), detailed as follows.

- **IC1** – The study must present computational approaches (tools, systems, algorithms) that support SRs.
- **EC1** – The study does not have an abstract.
- **EC2** – The study is an abstract or extended abstract without full text.
- **EC3** – The study is not a primary study. Studies considered editorials, lecture abstracts, tutorials, posters were excluded.
- **EC4** – The study is not written in English.
- **EC5** – The study is a copy or older version of another publication that was already considered. The most current version was considered.
- **EC6** – No access to the full article.
- **EC7** – The study does not address computational approaches to support SRs conduction in SE.

Data Storage The studies returned in the search activity were cataloged and stored. A data extraction form was used to collect the relevant data to answer the RQs. This form assisted in data extraction and synthesis procedures and can be used for updating or replication.

Assessment Before performing the mapping, a pilot test was conducted to verify its feasibility and suitability based on a pre-selected set of studies considered relevant to our investigation. Only one of the authors initially carried out study selection and data extraction activities. To reduce subjectivity, two other authors carried out these same activities on the entire sample. After selections, we measured the level of agreement between the results obtained from the reviewers in the selection process. To analyze the level of agreement, the kappa coefficient [2] was used, which is a statistical measure of agreement between researchers. The coefficient ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 indicates that there is no agreement and 1 indicates complete agreement. For this mapping, the global kappa coefficient obtained was 99.09%, whose interpretation, according to Landis and Koch [2], is in substantial agreement.

Search Strategy and Selection Process Candidate studies were searched systematically, as illustrated in Figure 1. The search process includes two steps, to be applied sequentially, as follows:

Fig. 1: Search and Selection Process

1. **Stage 1** – Initially, the *search string* was applied to the Scopus database with the necessary adaptations in three metadata fields (title, abstract and keywords). One thousand and one hundred and seventy-one (1171) studies related to the string were returned. Using the selection criteria and considering title, abstract and keywords, three researchers selected 48 studies as potentially relevant. Subsequently, the selection criteria were jointly applied by three researchers (with 91.49% agreement) considering the full text, resulting in a set of 20 studies (used as the initial set for snowballing). In the selection stage, studies published up to May 2024 were considered.

2. **Stage 2** – In a second stage, *Forward Snowballing* was conducted in the 20 studies selected in Stage 1. After performing *Forward Snowballing*, 690 studies were obtained. After applying the selection criteria to the title, abstract, and keywords, 44 studies remained. Finally, an analysis of the full text was performed, and after applying the selection criteria, 18 studies remained at this stage. As a final result, 38 studies were selected (20 from Scopus + 18 from *Forward Snowballing*). The replication package, together with the full list of references for the 38 selected studies references, is provided in the supplementary material to facilitate reproducibility, and its link is provided in the final of this paper.

We analyze each selected study to identify different facets for classifying the studies. The facets were defined according to RQ2 and RQ3. We systematically extract and review the most relevant data from the studies, thus iteratively evolving toward classification. The categories of these facets are presented below.

Approaches characteristics (RQ2): This facet aims to offer an overview of the proposed computational approach. We have identified three main categories: type of approach, accessibility, frequency of updates, input and output and usability.

Support SR (RQ3): This facet aims to know how the coverage/semi-automation approach works considering the main phases and activities of the SR process: Planning, Conducting and Reporting.

Regarding RQ4, we extracted and summarized the main challenges that have been explicitly stated in the studies.

References

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